

FABRICE REQUIER

WILD-LIVING HONEY BEES IN EUROPE:
COLONY DENSITY, SURVIVAL RATE AND CONSERVATION PLANS

*Le colonie non gestite di ape mellifera in Europa:
densità, tasso di sopravvivenza e programmi di conservazione*

The western honey bee *Apis mellifera* is an iconic species, and its importance for honey production and pollination services is widely acknowledged. However, it is also widely acknowledged that its health status is critical because it is threatened by multiples stressors, such as pathogens, pesticides, and lack of forage. While much attention is given to managed honey bee colonies, its fascinating existence in the wild is often overlooked. In this talk, I will present an overview of the ecology of wild-living honey bees with a specific attention to the native range of the species in Europe. I will present estimates of several critical ecological traits of wild-living honey bees in Europe such as the colony density, the population size and the survival rate. Moreover, I will present potential European conservation hotspots and proposal of conservation plans for the preservation of so far neglected wild-living honey bee populations in Europe.

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